

A Study on the Application of BOPPPS Teaching Model Based on Core Competence in English Classroom Reading Teaching

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Abstract: under the background of the core literacy of the discipline put forward by the New Curriculum Standard, it has become the top priority of school education to improve students' interest in reading, shape correct values, develop key abilities and form necessary character. As a new teaching model, BOPPPS helps to build hierarchical and measurable teaching modules. This model fully integrates the links of introduction, goal, pre-test, participatory learning, post-test and summary, and gradually guides students to read articles, grasp the main idea, learn to use grammar in real situations, and finally through homework and students' self-evaluation form, test the degree of students' achievement of teaching goals. In this paper, the classroom teaching of "He Spent about Twenty Hours in Space", the first unit reading course of English Module 7 of Grade 6, is taken as an example to carry out teaching design by using the six stages of BOPPPS teaching model, in order to provide reference for the effective implementation of English reading class in primary schools.

Key words: BOPPPS model; core literacy; primary school English; reading teaching

0. Introduction

The core literacy requirements put forward in the English Curriculum Standard for compulsory Education (2022 Edition) (hereinafter referred to as the "New Curriculum Standard") emphasize "putting learning into practice and giving priority to practice" ^[1]. Reading is an important form of practice, but in the process of learning, students generally lack interest in reading, lack of motivation ^[2], and reading teaching is generally fragmented and mechanized. In this context, the improvement and promotion of English reading teaching has become a top priority ^[3]. As a new teaching model, BOPPPS helps to build hierarchical and measurable teaching modules. This model fully integrates the links of introduction, goal, pre-test, participatory learning, post-test and summary ^[4], and gradually guides students to read articles, grasp the main idea, and learn to use grammar in real situations. Finally, through homework and students' self-evaluation form, test the degree of students' achievement of teaching goals.

The purpose of this study is to explore the current situation and problems of English classroom reading teaching based on core literacy, and to analyze its role and influence in cultivating students'

core literacy. The relevant data and materials are collected and sorted out through the methods of literature research, classroom observation and case analysis. The expected results will reveal the effective models and strategies of English classroom reading teaching based on core literacy, provide useful reference and guidance for English teachers, and improve the quality and effectiveness of English classroom reading teaching. At the same time, this study will help to promote the development of students' English reading ability, cultivate their core qualities such as language ability, thinking quality, cultural awareness and learning ability, and lay a solid foundation for students' all-round development and future study and life. The significance of this study is to enrich the theory and practice of English classroom reading teaching, promote the reform and development of English education, and contribute to the cultivation of high-quality talents who can meet the needs of the times.

1. Interpretation of BOPPPS teaching model.

The BOPPPS model originates from the Canadian teacher work ISW project, which is based on constructivism and communicative approach, emphasizing student-centered and improving student participation^[4]. The teaching model is student-centered, encourages students to participate and explore, and helps students build the ability of deep understanding and application of knowledge. It provides a structured teaching process for students to help teachers better organize and manage the classroom and improve students' learning effect. Its main characteristics are student-centered, emphasizing students' active participation and interaction; paying attention to the clarity of teaching objectives to make teaching activities more targeted; at the same time, timely understanding of students' learning through pre-test and post-test, easy to adjust teaching strategies.

The implementation steps are clear and clear: first, attract students' attention and stimulate interest in learning through the introduction; then clearly explain the learning goals to let students know clearly the tasks to be achieved; then carry out pre-tests to understand the initial state of students; in the process of participatory learning, encourage students to actively participate and cultivate their various abilities; post-test is used to evaluate students' learning effect; finally, summarize and strengthen key knowledge. The application of BOPPPS teaching model is not limited to 10 minutes, not only to a class, but also to a course. Through the introduction of the overview, the arrangement of the whole chapter and the examination requirements at the beginning of the course, students can look forward to the course, define their learning goals, and grasp their interest in learning. Pre-test is very important for students' participatory learning, and participatory learning should run through the learning process of the whole course. The view that teaching quality can be effectively improved through BOPPPS teaching mode. In addition, participatory learning and goal setting are important. The application advantage in teaching is very significant, it can effectively improve the teaching quality, make the teaching process more systematic and scientific, enhance students' learning enthusiasm and participation, improve learning effect, promote teachers' professional growth, and improve teaching ability.

Typically, the BOPPPS mode consists of the following six modules:

Table 1 BOPPPS schema

Modules	Main task
Bridge-in	Teachers ask questions and share relevant stories or examples.

Objective	Clear curriculum objectives and learning objectives.
Pre-assessment	Assess students' previous knowledge and understanding through quizzes or questions.
Participatory Learning	Group discussions, problem solving activities, case studies, etc.
Post-assessment	Evaluate the results of group projects, papers, lectures, etc.
Summary	The review emphasizes important knowledge points.

The above tasks form a complete reading teaching process in series, which mainly includes the following contents:

(1) Select the text. Teachers should choose appropriate reading materials in the light of curriculum objectives and learning conditions.

(2) content prediction. Teachers should give some hints according to what they have learned in this lesson, so that students can understand the content.

(3) read the text. Teachers should guide students to skim and read the text carefully to find out the general idea and details of the text.

(4) thinking expansion. Through the form of group cooperation and discussion, we can improve students' understanding of the text and divergence of thinking.

(5) summarize and reflect, summarize the learning achievements through inter-group evaluation, students' self-evaluation and teacher evaluation.

2. The application of BOPPPS teaching model in English reading teaching in junior middle school.

(1) text selection.

This case is an in-class reading material, which belongs to the theme context of "people and Society". This text belongs to the first unit He Spent about Twenty Hours in Space of module 7 in the second volume of Grade 6 (2013 edition) of Foreign language Teaching and Research Press. After integrating the learning content, teachers interpret the article from the perspective of "space", carry out reading teaching, explore the significance of the theme, learn the good quality of characters, stimulate students' interest in learning, cultivate patriotic enthusiasm, and carry out ideal education to achieve the goal of educating people. The discourse analysis is as follows: the text is a narrative about the deeds of Yang Liwei written by Yang Liwei's son. In October 2003, Yang Liwei went into space by Shenzhou V manned spaceship and flew in space for about 21 hours.

He did a lot of things in space, filmed videos, and then returned to Earth.

Yang Liwei's son is proud of his father and hopes to go to space one day.

The unit task is to introduce the life stories of role models in the simple past tense.

The teaching objectives of this course are as follows:

After this class, students will be able to:

1. grasp , read, speak and write words in class with the prompt of pictures and recordings;
2. correctly understand the text information and imitate the target language correctly and loudly with the help of text illustrations, text recordings, text animation, task lists.
3. retell the text according to the prompts, and describe events in simple past tense.
4. introduce the deeds of outstanding people, learn the qualities of celebrities and build their

dreams and love for the country.

(2) content prediction.

This part allows students to form learning expectations, connect their own experience with learning content, find cognitive gaps and generate learning motivation. Teachers can warm up the scene by playing videos, giving pictures, or organizing Mini Game to attract students' interest in reading and learning. Guide the students to think positively and have a preliminary understanding of what they have learned in this lesson. Let students introduce astronauts in simple language, know something about them, and activate their existing knowledge reserves. Through group discussion, students prepare materials, extract information, fully understand the topic, perceive the structure and content of the text, and have a preliminary understanding of the thematic meaning of this lesson, so as to stimulate students' interest in English communication, which is conducive to the cultivation of students' English core literacy. Teachers can give space photos and tips and ask questions: Do you know aliens? How much do you know? The student gives an answer, then gives some pictures of space, and then goes on to ask: What do you know about space? You can discuss in groups according to the following parts: size, color, weight, lives, ect. Leading from space to astronauts, that is, the theme of this course: But there must be some people there, who are they? Can you introduce us some of them? Ask the students to introduce some astronauts they know well. Led by astronauts to Yang Liwei, the protagonist of this class. The teacher gave a picture of Yang Liwei and asked the students to make an introduction: Who is he? Please introduce him to us. After the students answered, the teacher pointed out that the content of this lesson was related to Yang Liwei and asked the students to predict the main content of this lesson: Please make a guess about today's story. Finally, ask the students to read the article quickly and check whether the prediction is correct.

(3) read the text.

This part allows students to actively participate in and experience the learning content. Teachers mainly assign tasks to students and create situations so that students can participate deeply and make real interactions. In this way, students can deeply experience and recognize the learning content. Students understand the story, extract information, fully understand the text and perceive the thematic meaning of the text. under the guidance of teachers, through careful observation, they find the past tense of verbs, and independently sum up the changing rules of the past tense of verb words. then use it in the actual situation to solve problems, give students the opportunity to practice, and really apply the language to life. The teacher gives several questions for students to read with questions to explore the gist of the text: When did Yang Liwei sent into space? How did he went into space? What did he do in space? The teacher put the three questions side by side and asked the students to find out the changes in tenses. And find more examples in the article. After the students finish skimming, the teacher gives the question word When,Where,How,What happened to guide the students to find out the details of the article according to the question words, and then generalizes the text according to these question words.

(4) expansion of thinking.

This part is used to expand students' thinking and test whether students fully understand the teaching content. Teachers can test whether they have achieved the expected results or whether there is

a gap in understanding through writing and speaking exercises. Considering the knowledge structure and thinking ability of the senior students, and in order to exercise the students' comprehensive ability, this stage encourages the students to think actively under the background of the text, which not only practices the newly learned language, but also enriches the imagination. The teacher organizes student group discussions and gives the following hints: What will you do if you are sent into space? You can discuss in groups. After the students' discussion is completed, the representatives are selected to make a speech. Finally, the students are asked to evaluate each other between groups according to grammatical correctness and imagination.

(5) Summary and reflection.

The purpose of the summary is to summarize and sort out the content learned and leave a deep impression. Summary is the end of the learning stage, which provides teachers and students with the opportunity to review the learning content and summarize the results. At this stage, teachers first ask students to summarize their learning achievements in order to understand their mastery and memory of knowledge, and then supplement and guide them. At the end of the study, students can use this form to test the achievement of their learning goals, so as to facilitate students to check and fill the gaps and review and consolidate. Teachers organize students to think about the bright points and excellent qualities that can be learned from the characters, and to express their admiration for the outstanding people and the motherland. Finally, the teacher distributes the learning effect test form to the students (see table below). The design of the table is mainly based on the teaching objectives of this course, and new projects related to classroom cooperation are added. The effect of classroom group cooperative learning also plays a vital role in the learning results of this course.

Table 2 self-evaluation table of students' learning effect

In this class, you:	Mark your score				
Learn about basic information of Yang Liwei and space.	1	2	3	4	5
Can cooperate with your group members effectively.	1	2	3	4	5
Can grasp the admirable points of Yang Liwei.	1	2	3	4	5
Can use simple past tense to describe things happened in the past.	1	2	3	4	5

The summary and reflection of teaching can also be based on homework. Teachers assign open assignments and choose topics according to students' interests, and students can choose by themselves.

Must do homework: Use the simple past tense to introduce another famous astronaut and try to choose the words in the book.

Choose to do homework: Check the information to see what activities astronauts have in space and describe them in the general past tense.

Table 3 list of students' writing requirements

Perspectives	Requirements
Language	Brief, correct, no grammatical mistakes
Contents	Related to the passage
Structure	Clear and logical

3. Conclusion.

This thesis has achieved some results through the in-depth study of English classroom reading teaching based on core literacy. In the process of research, it is deeply aware of the importance and positive influence of core literacy in English classroom reading teaching.

The English classroom reading teaching model based on core literacy can not only improve students' reading ability, but also promote their all-round development. By cultivating students' language ability, thinking quality, cultural awareness and learning ability, we have laid a solid foundation for students' future. To sum up, with the deepening of education reform, under the background of "establishing morality and cultivating people", the use of BOPPPS teaching model in primary school English teaching has become an important choice, which not only defines the train of thought and direction for the current primary school English teaching innovation, but also enriches the educational connotation of English teaching.

As far as teachers are concerned, in the process of teaching design, it should give full play to the leading role of core literacy, determine curriculum objectives, select curriculum contents and innovate teaching methods on the basis of subject core literacy, construct hierarchical and measurable teaching modules based on BOPPPS teaching model, gradually guide students to read articles, grasp the main idea, learn to use grammar in real situations, and do a good job in timely detection and evaluation. In order to maximize students' participation and learning effect ^[7], and then help students to master scientific learning methods and learn to solve problems.

However, it is also aware that there are still some problems and challenges in practice, which need us to explore and improve constantly. It is need to further optimize teaching methods and improve teachers' professional literacy in order to better adapt to the changing educational environment.

Although this study has achieved some results, there are still many aspects that need to be further studied and discussed. It is believe that English classroom reading teaching based on core literacy will continue to play an important role. It will continue to devote ourselves to the research and practice in this field and contribute to the development of English education. It is also expected that more educators to pay attention to and participate in this research, jointly explore innovative teaching models and methods, and strive to cultivate a new generation of talents with core qualities.

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